

Supplementary Information

Detailed schematics and structural descriptions of the laboratory-built soil leaching simulation apparatus, including the adjustable slope platform, flow-control module, and vertical and lateral leachate collection units, are provided in the Supplementary Information (Figure S1).

Figure S1. Schematic illustration of the laboratory-built inclined leaching apparatus. (A) Three-dimensional view of the apparatus showing the main structural components. **(B)** Side view with numbered components: (1) water reservoir with constant-head overflow system; (2) perforated sample container (mesh size: 0.5 mm); (3) adjustable slope platform (0-25 deg range); (4) vertical leachate collection basin; (5) lateral leachate collection trough; (6) flow rate control valve; (7) drainage ports; (8) support frame with angle indicator. **(C)** Photograph of the apparatus during operation, showing a researcher applying PFOA solution to the quartz sand surface. **(D)** Conceptual diagram of the sampling strategy illustrating three sampling positions: (1) lateral runoff collected from the downslope edge; (2) vertical leachate (bottom) collected from beneath the sample container; (3) solid phase sampling from the center of the sand bed after leaching completion.